

The Entropic Cost of Information Decoding of a Quantum Free Particle

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It is well known that a quantum free particle with momentum p is represented by a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ and that it may interfere with a slit system if the slits are separated by about \hbar/p , i.e. a wavelength. Other diffraction and interference experiments may also occur. We suggest in this note, that $\exp(ipx)$ is a physical dynamical function which encodes the information p in a spatial manner, i.e. through a wavelength, and that decoding, i.e. interaction with an appropriate two slit apparatus etc, requires a cost of entropy, i.e. the entropy pattern created through the interference. We suggest that several measurements in quantum mechanics come at the cost of the generation of entropy.

Quantum Free Particle as an Information Function

We have suggested in previous notes that the quantum free particle wavefunction, and the wavefunction in general, is a built-in dynamic information or self-measurement function. In the free particle case, it encodes information, namely p momentum, in a spatial manner through a wavelength \hbar/p . As a result, instead of the particle hitting a target in order to demonstrate its p value, one may decode this value spatially by using an appropriate spatial decoder such as a two-slit apparatus with slit separation of \hbar/p , or single slit diffraction etc. There is a cost, however, of such a decoding measurement, namely in terms of spatial entropy production. In particular, two slit interference or diffraction produces a pattern with entropy. If the slits are very far apart compared with \hbar/p and the slit itself very wide, the particle simply passes through. There is no decoding of the p value and no entropy generation.

We suggest that other examples of such encoding and decoding also exist.

Bohm Aharonov Effect

The wavefunction of a charged particle passing through a vector magnetic potential A_{vec} such that p is not changed picks up a phase $\int_{(0,x)} A_{vec}(x')dx'$. This leads to an interference pattern when interference occurs with a particle which did not pass through A_{vec} . This interference pattern, in turn, represents additional entropy.

Single Particle Bound State

A single particle bound state involves interactions with a potential such that one has an average wavefunction: $W(x)=\sum_{p} a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The $a(p)$ take on special values such that one has average energy conservation at each x point, i.e.

$$\left(\sum_{p} a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)\right) / \left(\sum_{p} a(p)\exp(ipx)\right) + V(x)=E_n \quad ((1))$$

This is again encoded information related to the particular E_n value and results in an entropy pattern given by $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ used to generate Shannon's entropy: $-k \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x)W(x))$.

If a bound particle absorbs a photon and moves to a higher E_n state, a different entropic pattern characterizes or decodes this state. Thus, states are represented by entropy patterns.

The bound state case is interesting because it encodes information about different $\exp(ipx)$ s. If one only had $\exp(ipx)$, then a two-slit interference experiment is needed to generate entropy as $W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ and displays no information about p . If one has different $\exp(ipx)$ s, then $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields an interference pattern (created by $V(x)$). Thus the signature of seeing information in these cases is an entropy pattern or entropy generation.

The higher the bound energy, the more the order, i.e. sharper resolution, but this requires energy input. A high energy bound state will spontaneously decay to a higher entropy (less resolution) state by emitting a photon. Thus, a self-measurement exists in a bound state as manifested by the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ which is the spatial probability one may use in a Shannon's entropy calculation. The measurement is automatically done and the entropy automatically exists because an interaction (measurement with $V(x)$) has occurred.

In other words, we suggest that various quantum results, are measurements manifested through entropic patterns, i.e. the measurement of an E_n or a p is equivalent to a certain entropy pattern (and hence entropy)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ encodes information about p spatially, namely through a spatial wavelength \hbar/p . To decode this value, one requires a two slit apparatus with slits about \hbar/p apart (or an analogous apparatus). The price is the generation of an entropy pattern. We suggest that a single particle bound system also produces such an entropy pattern as the particle interacts with $V(x)$. Similarly, interference of a particle which has moved through a magnetic potential which does not change p and one which did not, also generates an interference pattern. Thus, some measurements in quantum mechanics are manifest through an interference pattern, i.e. at the cost of spatial entropy.

For the case of a bound particle, one may reduce spatial entropy by absorbing a photon and moving to a more ordered (less entropic state), but such a state will spontaneously decay by emitting a photon, down to a less ordered, more entropic one. Again, the entropy is a signature of the measurement of the state, say E_n . It is not just the case that one has an energy of e_n , or a momentum p , but there is a specific entropy associated with. In the case of $\exp(ipx)$ one does not explicitly see (decode) this entropy unless interference occurs with say a 2-slit apparatus. Thus, decoding or measuring comes at the price of entropy generation. In the case of E_n , interference of a single particle automatically occurs, so E_n automatically is associated with an interference pattern.